

Samaritan Worship on the Meadow in the Time of Straying

by

Ruairidh MacMhanainn Bóid ¹

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I. The climate of feeling

It is known from the second notice of the Dositheans ² by Abu 'l-Fateh (hereinafter A.F.) that they discontinued sacrifices before the time of Dositheos. Their rationale was that there could not be sacrifices without the Mosaic Tabernacle. It could reasonably have been asked how it was that their ancestors had had sacrifices for centuries after the occultation of the Tabernacle. Doubtless this objection came up. In my book *A Samaritan Plan of Religious History* I argued that the time of sacrifices was over and people could not see any sense in having them. The answer to any objection would have been that the ancestors had not thought hard enough. The other party, the Sebuaeans, came up with a different justification for not having sacrifices: since whole burnt offerings are not burnt up by fire from heaven these days, it must be the will of God not to have sacrifices. The Sebuaeans were more blatant than the Dositheans. They made up a story that the end of sacrifices had been made known on the return from the Exile. It can be supposed that if anyone objected that sacrifices had been kept up for a couple of centuries after then, the answer would have been that it was out of ignorance.

The Sebuaean argument for not having sacrifices would not have caused distress, but the Dosithean one certainly caused distress to some people. Most Dositheans were content to keep going as things were, with an expectation of change in the undefined future, and this became the general Dosithean outlook eventually. Some people, however, could not forget about sacrifices. They felt compelled to dramatise how unsatisfactory the present situation was. Some of them thought they could make the present situation an opportunity for reflection. Some thought they could go further and set up a provisional situation that would be an improvement. It would be possible to speak of the range of feelings about the absence of the Tabernacle, but actions are more definitely documented, and feelings can be gauged from them. Two factions dramatised the need for change in the world by abandoning the Mountain. One reaction showed regret but expectation. The other expressed a need for a complete new start, but with hope for the future expressed both in words and in the concept of the status of Melchizedek.

¹ **The author has no connection with the State of Israel.**

² They were called Sadducees originally, and seem to have kept this as their official name for internal use. See my book, p. 120. Early Christian authors are confused, and so are some modern academics trying to make sense of what they say. In this article it will be assumed that the reader has read Part II and Part VI of my book and my article *The First Notice* and won't need continual references for verification of single facts. Data will be given again here if needed for the flow of the presentation.

It must be borne in mind that feelings were strong, sometimes overwhelming. This is obvious from the drasticness of what was done by two Dosithean factions. Feelings about how unsatisfactory the quality of reality was were intense in the culture and society of the time and place. This is the time of sprouting of Gnosticism. Gnosticism was not trying to understand a religion or religious texts with insight. It was not trying to understand reality at some level and live as part of reality. Gnosticism does not mean working towards gnōsis, that is, deep insight or transcendent insight. Gnosticism is a word made up in modern Latin (sic) and copied in a lot of European languages as a name for manifestations of a climate of thought that had no specific name in its time. Often the use is narrowed down to mean sects that accepted the classic Gnostic Myth. Either way, whether vague or narrow in application, the word refers to a climate of thought in which reality itself, not just circumstances, is felt to be unnatural or not right. From this comes the thought that reality is not really real, and the search for escape to what is really real and not pretend real. This leads to the conviction that Creation is not from God and knowledge coming from outside Creation will give escape. The manifestation of world-denying Gnosticism was pernicious. The drastic behaviour of some Dositheans was a lot healthier.

Reactions to the ending of sacrifices were reactions to a feeling of unsatisfactoriness, with the ending of sacrifices standing in for the occultation of the Tabernacle and the coming of the Fānūta, but at this time the Fānūta had turned from a concept about the workings of Providence into a concretisation of bad reaction to the undeniable sober fact that a lot was wrong. The reactions were different ways of behaving so as to act out the right mindset and thereby strengthen it.

The documentation will now be looked at anew.

II. Sakte's pavilion, the Vexatious Abomination

It is generally assumed that the last part of the second notice of the Dositheans by A.F. and the third notice give all developments in Dosithean thought after the death of Dositheos. Now that I have explained the content of these notices, which had been mostly unintelligible till then, in Part VI of my book, it is time to show that with this knowledge more signs of development can be seen in the first notice.

It says in A.F. 82:12 – 13, “They asserted that the scripture they had, by the Children of the Apostle, had in it that God might be served [by sacrifices] in the Land of Zawīlah till he could be served [by sacrifices] on Mt. Gerizim”. The Land of Zawīlah is the Balāṭah Meadow, the Meadow of the Kavod, the Plain of Vision, the Shechem Meadow. See my article *The First Notice of the Dositheans*, column 371 middle. Zawīlah is the Arabic equivalent of Abbīla אַבְיִלָּה in Genesis II:11. The verb translated here as “serve” implies offering sacrifices and will unequivocally mean that in the right context, but in a different context would mean doing the equivalent in a liturgy. This range of meaning is used in the Arabic expression for **offering** the Christian Mass. Without knowing the context, the formula could have come from either

Sakte's followers or the Qaṭṭīṭā'i or the authors of II Enoch, the last two of which might have been the same. It will be shown that it comes from Sakte. I disagree with Olson on this.

Not all of what is reported before this formula fits Sakte. He could not have made up this tightening of the rules of menstruation because he is known to have decreed loosening in some respects. Neither could he have made up the tightening of the rules of contamination from a dead human body that is recorded because it is known that he did the opposite. Sakte did forbid use of the formula "Blessed is his Name forever". He did demand use of the word "God" and not Shēma, "the Name", which is a reference to the Tetragrammaton. The formula about worship on the Meadow is quoted straight after these two demands. We either have to assume multiple sources, or assume a single source that agreed with Sakte on two points, discontinuing use of the formula "Blessed is his Name forever" and discontinuing use of the title Shēma. If it is a single list, then the formula about worship on the Meadow is in an odd place. It will be shown that the answer is that there are two lists, not less and not more. Once the place of division between them is seen, the whole notice suddenly has logical structure.

First come five halachot, with the fifth, on graves, having two parts. **All these are explainable as haḥmarot.** This list does not come from Sakte, since some of it contradicts his principles. These haḥmarot are in the rigorous spirit of the Bā'ūnā'i. This faction would have been concerned with cleanness of any pool because of their concern with immersion and saying their morning prayer in a state of cleanness. However, the two haḥmarot on uncleanness from graves and counting days of purification directly oppose Sakte's principles and might instead be a deliberate statement of rejection of one part of his basic principle by most Dositheans.

There is another note further on, in the second part of the notice, the list about Sakte, saying they did the same as the Jews in counting the days up to Pentecost. If the compiler worked centuries after the end of Sakte's faction, he could have listed items on which they agreed with all other Dositheans in the list taken from the description of the practice of Sakte's followers. They did agree with all other Dositheans on having a calendar with all months having thirty days, and not having sacrifices. There might be more on the list about Sakte that was common to all Dositheans. What is said about rules for making decisions in cases of doubt could well be examples of this. The two haḥmarot on the Sabbath right at the end of the second list are likely to be specific to Sakte, since they are separated from the haḥmarot of the first list, and are in line with two known haḥmarot of his. See below. The second list might not be meant to be a list of what divided Sakte from other Dositheans made by the compiler, but a summary of part of a handbook for Sakte's followers, couched as a report by the compiler.

It can be seen that the compiler does not know there are different kinds of Dositheans, since he puts a list of five haḥmarot that include two not agreeing with Sakte's tendency at the start of a list certainly describing Sakte's followers without any remark.

After the first list, the five haḥmarot, comes information about Sakte and his followers. First there are two taqqanot, one being to modify a liturgical formula and one being not to use a term that recalled the Tetragrammaton. It is recorded in the third notice of the Dositheans that

it was specifically Sakte, and not Dositheans in general, that discontinued the use of a substitution Shēma for the Tetragrammaton and replaced it by the word Ēlūwem, God. (The English word “substitution” is not precise enough. The Hebrew word is kinnūy. This could be called a direct reference. The word Ēlūwem is a replacement). Then there is the statement of doctrine about worship on the Meadow. Then comes a list that shows some structure. First comes information about the calendar. This does not mean Sakte disagreed with other Dositheans on the calendar. Al-Qirqisāni reports that Dositheans in general have a calendar with months of thirty days. So does Abu ’l-Fateḥ. The two reports on the length of months are independent of each other and must be accepted as they stand. See my book, p. 119. This is the logical place to put information about the calendar, before mentioning the Festivals. The next two pieces of data are two general rules following from the basic principle distinctive to Sakte, which are expressed in the form of halachah. They discontinued observance of the Festivals because of their doctrine that the Mountain had no special status if the sanctuary building did not have the Mosaic Tabernacle in it. They discontinued the Passover slaughter, which is not a sacrifice, for the same reason. The Passover slaughter is done outside the sacred area, but is invalid if there is no sacred area and no valid sanctuary building. They discontinued giving terumah to Priests because there was no valid sanctuary. Then comes the counting of the days till Pentecost. Putting this here might mean Sakte disagreed with other Dositheans, but might not. It is more likely to be an observation by the compiler, since he adds his own comment. (Unless the comment is by A.F.). This is the logical place to mention the counting of days from Passover to Pentecost, after mentioning the Festivals. This datum shows that although Sakte’s faction did not have sacrifices and did not go up the Mountain on the Festivals, they still had special synagogue services for the Festivals on the Meadow. Then comes a lot of information about leprosy of houses in two parts. Leprosy of houses never happened, so all this must be illustration of two rules on deciding in case of doubt or apprehension of possibility ששח and then doubt about something doubtful or doubt about an apprehension of possibility ששחשח . This long explanation of a rule is nearly at the end. Right at the end come two haḥmarot about the Sabbath.³ Subject order is obvious. There are two taqqanot, then there is the basic doctrine of worship on the Meadow, then there is statement of basic principle of the status of the Mountain expressed as halachah which goes with the statement about worship on the Meadow, then some explanation of method, then two haḥmarot on the Sabbath. The calendar is mentioned before the rule about Festivals because the Festivals follow the calendar. The reckoning of Pentecost follows the rule about the Festivals and terumah because it needed to be clarified that although there are not to be sacrifices at the sacred place on the Festivals, there must be special synagogue services on the Meadow for the Festivals. The comment that they

³ A.F. 162:6 – 7 “He forbade sex and immersion on the Sabbath”. The readers the author had in mind would know there was no connection between the two, since after immersion cleanness only comes into effect at sunset. Bowman’s translation “He forbade repeated immersion on the Sabbath” can be quoted here as an example of his four constant faults all at once: inadequate command of Arabic syntax; misuse of dictionaries by mechanical unthinking use; ignorance of Samaritan halachah; **and not caring about whether his translation made sense**. I nearly always decline to mention Bowman’s translations in my publications because anyone with a real command of Arabic, along with normal habit of thought about what could normally happen or be done or said by a normal person, will see what is wrong. The purpose of publication is not to waste the reader’s time with lists of **unnecessary** mistakes.

made their offensiveness public shows that the compiler is making a report to inform outsiders. These two single items about the Sabbath are haḥmarot. This fits Sakte's two other known haḥmarot on the Sabbath, one not allowing sex on that day and the other not allowing immersion. There are five clear parts to the list, in logical order, from five separate chapters of a book. They are taqqanot, statement of principle, consequence of principle, a bit about method, haḥmarot.

The evidence is that there were two factions that discontinued observance of the pilgrim festivals on the Mountain, not more. Each faction had a coherent justification for what looked odd from the outside. Each had a structure of some kind on the Meadow, both of which are mentioned in ch. XII of the Asaḥir. The authors of II Enoch had something better than argument, the authority of the Torah in the form of confirmation of the validity of sacrifices on the Meadow if there is no single Deuteronomic sanctuary. Sakte had a different approach. He claimed to be the authoritative interpreter of Dositheos. This is why his followers *asserted*, instead of just stating, that their book said that God could be served on the Meadow in the present era. This is why they said the **fact** was in the book, instead of saying the book said this, and what it said was right. See my book, p. 130. A.F. 163:1: "He said he had not departed from what is implicit in what was said by Dositheos". We are not told which axiom he had in mind. It might be this one. A.F. 162:6: "There is no holiness in the Time of Straying [or Error]". It can be assumed that the axiom was old in his time and not invented by him, since the Sebuaean equivalent is attested. A. F. 27:2—4 "In the Turning Away Fānūta there is no perfection". The Sebuaeans used this axiom to state --- not argue --- that sacrifices had been discontinued by divine decree. See my book pp. 115 -- 116. Long before then it had been decided by all Dositheans (using the term anachronistically for convenience) that without a satisfactory sanctuary building with the Tabernacle inside, there could not be any sacrifices. If the axiom goes back to Dositheos, it would have meant that as the grade of holiness, as opposed to cleanness, only has relevance to the sanctuary and Priests when officiating in the sanctuary and in front of it, then if there is no satisfactory sanctuary there is no grade of holiness and therefore sacrifices are forbidden. (Officiating includes eating terumah away from the sanctuary). This argument could just as well be seen as a statement of two facts each demanding the other. Sakte probably argued that the grade of holiness was only given to the Mountain by the sanctuary, and since the present sanctuary building was not in a state of holiness because the Mosaic Tabernacle was not inside it, the Mountain was like any other mountain, as he put it.

The statement of principle on worship on the Meadow in this notice does not come from the community that wrote the Second Book of Enoch, though Olson argues at length that it does. For a start, if the statement is quoted from writings of this community, it has no place in a notice about halachah. Olson does not address this difficulty. If it comes from Sakte, it fits perfectly. It sits after two known edicts of his and before a record of what he is known to have taught about observance of the Festivals. Olson makes much of the use of the symbolic name of the Meadow in this statement. The name is Abbīla אַבִּילָא from Genesis. (Masoretic form Ḥavīla). It is perfectly true that this symbolic name was used by the authors of II Enoch, but anyone else could use it whenever appropriate. The name symbolises the connection between the Mountain and the Meadow. In a way not fully understood it expresses the concept of the

Meadow having some degree of holiness. Sakte did not just announce the negative principle that the Mountain had no special holiness in the Time of Straying: he announced the other side, the positive side, that the Meadow had a special quality as compared to other places.

It might have been expected that Epiphanius would have heard the name of this party even if he did not know anything about it. He doesn't know anything about any of the Samaritan parties but manages to fill up a lot of pages under the heading of heresy no. XII with waffle. He thinks he knows the Sebuaeans moved the date of Passover by six months, because he does not know that what is called Jewish New Year is on the first of the seventh. See my book p. 103. This blunder of his has been copied as if a historical datum. This has been done by Jews, such as S. J. Isser in his book on the Dositheans, in the belief that knowledge of Judaism is genetically transmitted. Beyond this disaster, Epiphanius doesn't make a single assertion about any party or faction in all the pages on Samaritan parties and factions. Sebuaeans and Dositheans are known. I've explained the name Essenes in Part II of my book. The obvious name needing to be looked at is the Gorthēnoi or Gorthēnoi. Both forms show up in the mss. of Epiphanius's work. The first form can be explained as inner-Greek development from the second. This name in the form Gorthēnoi is used by Hegesippus along with names of other Samaritan parties and factions though he thinks them all to be Christian. See Pummer's collection. This name has long seemed intractable. What is needed is to find the Hebrew or Aramaic name with a Greek ending stuck on and work out what it means. This demands a knowledge of the religion of Israel and a knowledge of the Torah, but nearly all commentators have been Christian theologians. The Aramaic behind this would be Gortā'i, the plural gentilic from the definite form gorta, with a corresponding indefinite gūra. The meaning is the place where you stay as opposed to where you live. The form does not seem to be attested, but it is regular and predictable. The form giyyor which would have the definite giyyūra is used with a possessive suffix in ms. A of the Samaritan Targum in Genesis XXVIII:4 to translate **בְּמִדְבָּר** with a possessive suffix. The Meadow is where you are staying and waiting till you go up to the top of Mt. Gerizim when the Mosaic Tabernacle has manifested itself. The verse in the Torah behind the name Gortā'i is Exodus II:22. In ms. A of the Samaritan Targum it says **אֵלֶּיךָ יִשְׂרָאֵל וְאֵלֶּיךָ יִשְׂרָאֵל**. Moses never got to Mt. Gerizim. He never got to Canaan. His time outside was preparation of the way to let others get to Mt. Gerizim. The time was used purposefully. The title they gave themselves was a reminder that the Time of Straying must be a time of advancement, not passive waiting. If my proposed etymology of the name is right, the name would have fitted Sakte's slogan, "From this pavilion we will go up to Mt. Gerizim". **Gorta would have been the name of the place where the pavilion stood, and then the name of the pavilion. It was not just a place of teaching and worship, but an expression of a concept.** The tashgiyyūta is the equivalent of Fānūta, which literally means turning the face away. It is the word lying behind the Arabic word *ḍalāl* used by A.F. in the third notice of the Dositheans at 162:6 and 164:3. The equivalence is certain at 164:3, where it is contrasted with the Time of Favour. There is a play on the three meanings of the Aramaic word tashgiyyūta, going astray and being wrong and being confused, which is kept in the Arabic equivalent.

The question as to whether the Gorthēnoi are the movement that wrote II Enoch, who are probably the Qaṭṭīā'i, or whether they are Sakte's followers, needs careful attention.

Neither Epiphanius nor his source have any information from observation. Against this is the consideration that if the information in the Christian source is not from observation, it must come from Samaritans. Putting aside the question of how certain we can be that the authors of the Second Book of Enoch and the Qaṭṭā'i are the same, it has to be asked whether Samaritans at the time would have put either of them on a list of Samaritan parties and factions. The Qaṭṭā'i are in the historical survey used by A.F. but the entry could be understood as implying that they stopped being Israelites. Against this is the consideration that there was a name for them that they had not made up themselves. They would not have described themselves as nuisances or people that cause difficulties. The remaining Samaritans would not have made up a name for them if there had not been contact. It is not safe to assume that the Qaṭṭā'i or the party that wrote II Enoch would have stopped all worship on the Mountain. Besides this, other Samaritans would have used the Meadow as well for synagogue services. The Mountain had holiness before the Mosaic dispensation in the same way as the Meadow.

The authors of ch. XII of the *Asaṭir* are pleased with the removal of the Troublemakers, who were some of the Jews living in Samaritan territory. (Text and translation of chapters XI and XII in my book, Part IV). See *Asaṭir* XII:9 – 10 with the commentary. They hope for the destruction of the Vexatious Abomination and after that the Shechem Sacred Enclosure. See *Asaṭir* XII:11 – 14 with the commentary. If there are two structures one must be Sakte's pavilion and the other the theatre-like structure known to Eusebius. (In my article *Social Anomie in the First Three Centuries of Islam* on column 29 I mistakenly identified the two structures with each other). The name of the second structure fits a sacred area with a surrounding solid structure and so fits his description. The Samaritans would have needed to have a name for the faction that put up the structure described by Epiphanius. In spite of all this, it is not plausible that any Samaritan would have readily classed the faction that built this structure as Samaritan and readily put its name on a list. Neither is it plausible that any Samaritan would have counted any faction that had sacrifices on the Meadow as Samaritan. The Gorthēnoi are not the faction that put up the roofless structure mentioned by Eusebius, they are not the faction that wrote II Enoch, and they are not the Qaṭṭā'i. Identification of all three of these last with each other is indicated.

By elimination, the followers of Sakte are left as the Gorthēnoi. Epiphanius is confused, but his source seems to have put the Gorthenians with the Dositheans against the Sebuaeans, and seems to have known of both Sebuaean Essenes and Dosithean Essenes. This is argued at length in my book, pp. 103 – 104. We still have to be careful about using this information, because the system might only have been to put the Sebuaeans against everyone else. This is how Epiphanius reads his source. On the other hand, he does not automatically set the Essenes against the Sebuaeans, so his source probably did have a picture of Sebuaeans including Essene Sebuaeans as against Dositheans including Essene Dositheans with Gorthenians. If the Gorthenians were Sakte's followers, this would fit. A Samaritan, whether Sebuaean or Dosithean, would certainly have counted Sakte's followers as Samaritans.

This raises the question of the date of the list used by Epiphanius. When would Sakte's faction have died out? It would have been before Epiphanius wrote, but that is not a difficulty

if he got it from a Christian record. The question does not need to be answered for the purpose of this investigation, but it would be useful to find an answer for future reference.

The list used by Hegesippus is hopeless. He thinks Samaritans are Christians that he can label heretics. The list used by Eusebius must then be later than Hegesippus. Hegesippus's dates of birth and death are not known exactly. The precise dates bandied about are taken from dodgy evidence. His death can be put somewhere between 170 and 190. If he lived to the age of seventy, he would have been born between 100 and 120, and if his book was written after he turned forty, it would have been written after 140 or after 160 AD. If the list used by Eusebius is later than that, it must be later than 140 or later than 160. This gives a surprisingly late date for the survival of Sakte's faction. The information might have been out of date.

Let's try to work out the date of the end of the faction by reckoning from when Dositheos died at the age of 28. This date can only be known approximately, so all dates reckoned from it will be approximate. Then estimates of length of stages after that can only be approximate. Still, an approximation of an approximation gives you a broad date range of high probability, which is a lot better than nothing. It gives a latest possible date, which is what is needed here. We start with the death of Dositheos at a young age. Christian writings are vague and not entirely in agreement, but they put him before Jesus. Now to Sakte's period of activity. First we have to date the figure of Simon the Samaritan in Christian writings. This Simon is a phantom. Sometimes he is the undated legendary author of a book known to have been used by most Samaritans, sometimes the founder of a Samaritan religious party, sometimes the personification of Samaritan religion, sometimes a caricature of Jesus before he was taken over and rewritten by Christianity (portrayed this way in the Clementine books), sometimes a reminiscence of Dositheos, sometimes a couple of these at once. When this Simon is given a date, sometimes he is Dositheos, sometimes Sakte, though sometimes other things as well. The commonly asserted connection of Dositheos with John the Baptist comes from careless reading. The person mentioned in this place in the different forms of the Clementine book started off with the Bā'ūnā'i, who had hegemony straight after Dositheos died. This person is Sakte, who wrested authority away from the Bā'ūnā'i. See my book, p. 53. See Part VI of my book on the order of developments within the Dosithean party. If we allow twenty years for confusion and then hegemony of the Bā'ūnā'i, the start of Sakte's activity can be put within a range of ten years before to ten years after 25 AD. If he was active for 35 to 45 years he would have died between 50 and 80 AD. The opposition policy arrived at by most members of the Dosithean party would have been attractive. This was expressed in the formula "Mt. Gerizim is holy, as he [God] said, and the House is on it. What is possible is to be carried out on it and what is not possible is not to be carried out". The verse Genesis XXVIII:17 is ambiguous as to whether the House of God and the Gate of Heaven are the same place, probably on purpose. Notice that it has been decided that Lūza, where Jacob was, is on the Mountaintop. Sakte would have put it on the Meadow at Balāṭah or Kafr Qalīl. This was one of the warrants from the Torah for his doctrine. The other would have been Exodus XXV:8 as it would have been interpreted by all Dositheans. It can plausibly be conjectured that they interpreted "sanctuary" maqdash מִקְדָּשׁ in this verse as mashkan מִשְׁכָּן on the basis of the verb in the same clause and the same noun in the next verse. The argument would have been that a mashkan is not a building, but a set of

curtains. There can be a building to house the mashkan, but the building is not the maqdash. His authority was supported partly by his claim to have unique insight into the depths of what was said by Dositheos. It seems unlikely that there would have been adherents to his faction for longer than 40 years after he died, which means the faction would have been amalgamated with the great majority of Dositheans between 80 and 125 AD. This is a much broader range than might be hoped for, but it is a lot better than nothing. It is helpful in one respect. Sakte's faction must have disappeared or changed into something inoffensive before composition of ch. XII of the Asaṭīr, which was after the start of the Jewish revolt in 132 but before the end of Hadrian's reign on his death in mid 138.

The considerations in these last two paragraphs fit in with what is said in ch. XII of the Asaṭīr. In verse 11 it says the people will demolish the Vexatious Abomination. It does not say it will be destroyed by outsiders, but rather will be taken down by the faction that put it up, because its time is over. *A more sober statement might have been that the unutterably offensive symbolic big tent or flimsy awning was replaced by something solid looking more like a study house meant for long term use that was only theoretically temporary, signalling a doctrine that was acceptable or not annoying enough to worry about.* This will be explained. It is after that or at that time that the offence of the Sanctuary of Alien Religion ends, as it says in verse 17. This really was the end of any feasible plans to revolt and set up the Jerusalem temple again. That this is the designation of the Jerusalem temple is made clear in the chapter before in XI:15. The last traces are wiped out by fire, according to this verse. There might really have been sulphur used, as the verse says. The end of the Vexatious Abomination is mentioned after the mention of removal of hostile Jewish forces from Samaria. It need not be assumed that this removal of disruption to administration was after the start of the Jewish revolt in 132. It could have been a few years before. It can be concluded that Sakte's tent was taken down or his awning was taken apart --- not demolished --- between about 125 and 136.

III. The Shechem Sacred Enclosure

There was another faction with a structure on the Meadow. In ch. XII of the Asaṭīr the structure is called the Shechem Sacred Enclosure. The Hebrew word used means an open hieron with a wall round it. Eusebius had heard a description of it. He describes it as theatre-like, which would mean it was roofless. It would be reasonable to identify this structure as the place of sacrifice of the community that wrote II Enoch. Olson has gone into this and there is no need to go over the considerations again here.

The authors of II Enoch are probably the Qaṭṭīṭā'i mentioned in the catalogue in A.F.'s second notice on the Dositheans. One of the reasons for supposing this is that the Asaṭīr only knows of two offensive structures on the Meadow. The other reason is that affinities can be seen. These people said **all** mitsvot had been ended. This is not a difference of degree compared to Sakte, but expression of a sharply different doctrine. They symbolically went through a graveyard on the Sabbath. We might guess that it was the graveyard of the High Priests next to Balāṭah on the Meadow at the foot of the Mountain, next to where Jacob camped and had his vision. The Second Book of Enoch makes it clear that before the giving of the Torah there was

no uncleanness from dead human bodies. It lays it on with a trowel. The Qaṭṭā'i went through the graveyard on the Sabbath to announce this. They would have done it on the Sabbath because they maintained that the status of the Sabbath does not come from the mitsvot of the Mosaic dispensation but goes back to divine decree on completion of Creation. If it was this faction wrote II Enoch, there are implications. They are said to have expressed their faith in a formula saying that God would restore the Mosaic Tabernacle. At first sight, II Enoch does not seem to express this expectation. On looking at what it says about Melchizedek, the picture changes. It must be emphasised that we don't know what they expected Melchizedek or the line of Priests from him to accomplish. (Melchizedek and his line are not always sharply distinguished from each other). The authors probably thought it was obvious, but it isn't. This article is not the place to try to answer this question. What needs to be said for the present purpose can be picked up from the picture of Melchizedek or his line in Olson's book. One of the important characteristics of Melchizedek or his line is that they are usually out of sight, but they are permanent. We are not told why they have to be permanent, but what can be picked up is that they assure the successful working of a divine plan, from which it can be supposed that they are needed for the coming of the Torah.

The Qaṭṭā'i knew what they were doing in making Enoch the main focus of their presentation of their theory of the relationship between worship on the Meadow and worship on the Mountain, with Melchizedek a necessary part. It is not all that clear to us now. It can be supposed that this line of thought led to the later minority opinion that the Tā'eb is Enoch, not Joshua. In the end the disagreement might not matter much, since both derive their status from Moses. (Saying this about Enoch might seem startling, but Olson's argument is convincing. See his book, chapter 6).

Olson thinks one of the main purposes of chapters I to X of the Asaṭīr to be refutation of the authors of the Second Book of Enoch. His argument is compelling. Whether he is right in saying the authors were Dositheans is another matter. His main proof is that they put the altar built by Adam on the Meadow and not on the Mountain. I used that argument myself in an earlier version of my book. I now see that it does not hold up. The Dositheans never disparaged the Mountain in relation to the Meadow. They regretted the temporary eclipse of its status. Everyone agreed that every important personage in the history of the righteous had built an altar on the Meadow, with the single exception that there was an old disagreement as to whether Jacob built his altar on the Mountain or at the foot at Balāṭah. My proposal that chapters XI and XII are not from the authors of chapters I to X has to be discarded. It is still possible that chapters XI and XII are tacked on, or perhaps only chapter XII. The indications of Sebuaean outlook in chapters XI and XII remain. There is nothing in chapters I to X that is distinctively Sebuaean or Dosithean. The book might well have been common property.

Olson argues convincingly that the authors of the first ten chapters of the Asaṭīr tried to make both Enoch and Melchizedek seem unimportant, in reaction to the doctrine of the authors of II Enoch. I would like to add the observation that this policy left a permanent trace. Material about these two was lost. One of the two late Arabic collections of old commentary on Genesis leaves both of them out altogether, and the other says a few words in passing that are correct

but obvious and don't show knowledge of any special qualities of either. The commentary from the early thirteenth century leaves both out of its set of disquisitions.

At the end of my article *An Ancient Form of the Samaritan Concept of the Tā'eb* I mentioned that Dositheos was seen as being both the prophet like Moses (but not the second Moses) and someone like Enoch. Olson goes into the connection between Enoch and Moses at length. *I would now like to suggest that part of the reason why there is no clear tradition of what Dositheos was thought to have accomplished or what exactly was meant by the terms the Prophet like Moses or the Second Prophet is that this was all deliberately obscured in the process of trying to make Enoch seem unimportant.* The expectation of the return of Enoch or his equivalent survived in the minority opinion that the Tā'eb would be like Enoch, not Joshua. In the end this might not be a big disagreement, since Joshua was given some of the spirit that was on Moses, and Olson argues that Moses is somehow the power behind Enoch. This sounds far-fetched at first, but the arguments he gives in chapter 6 of his book hold up.

IV. The end of worship on the Meadow

Even within Sakte's lifetime, there was an organised push within the Dositheans against his policy, and opponents of his policy greatly outnumbered supporters of it. See my book pp. 120 to 123. A formula was devised. A.F. 163:5—7: "They said Mt. Gerizim was holy, as he [God] said, and the House is on it. What is written must be carried out on it and what is not possible is not to be carried out". It needs to be added to what was set out in my book that behind this formula was far more than a slogan. Behind it lies some hard thinking. The Dositheans were forced to define the metaphysical status of the Mountain. They had to formulate how it was that the Mountain had been recognised as holy before the giving of the Torah, but was given a place by the Torah. The practical outcome was that the status of the Mountain was emphasised. **The feeling of need for the sanctuary was assuaged as the Mountain took on what had been the function of the Meadow before the giving of the Torah.** It is known that what was called the Dosithean Pavilion survived in use till the early eighth century AD, and was rebuilt at least once. See my article *Social Anomie in the First Three Centuries of Islam*. Its message must have been refined. *I propose that the new formula devised in reaction to the Gorthenians was accepted by the former Gorthenians themselves, but with their own emphasis. The formula acknowledges that the state of the Mountaintop is unsatisfactory in the present era, so for the former Gorthenians the Pavilion would have been needed to make sure this was not forgotten. This way of looking at the need for the Pavilion would not have offended other Dositheans even if they thought it was carrying on too much. At the same time it was accepted by the former Gorthenians that the Mountain was holy without the Tabernacle, so everything except sacrifices is possible and therefore obligatory. The former Gorthenians must have seen an argument for a way of recognising the validity of the Festivals in the present era even without sacrifices. This sounds improbable till you consider that the other Dositheans and the Sebuaeans and the Jews managed to formulate a rationale for just that, each in their own way. The former Gorthenians must have come up with an argument of their own that suited them.* At the moment there is no way of reconstructing what the argument might have been. At the same time they would have had to drop their old label, since the

argument behind it could not be used any more, which would explain why record of the name vanished so early on, even though the Pavilion stood for centuries after.

Sakte would have read Genesis XXVIII:17 as saying that Lūza was on the Meadow at Balāṭah. Eusebius puts Lūza here. The spot is probably Balāṭah. In the new reading the ambiguity in the verse would have been resolved by saying that it says “this” with two different predicates, the House of God and the Gate of Heaven, because there was some separation and the top of the crag was higher up, and it says “this” and not “that” in the second clause because Jacob was on the Mountaintop. The new general Dosithean reading formulated to counter him was artificial, though it would not have been thought so.

Defence against polemic by Jews is simpler if you stick to the validation of the Mountain in Jacob’s vision rather than what place is meant in the instructions for the sanctuary in Deuteronomy. It might only be coincidence that the Samaritan woman in John IV argues for the status of Mt. Gerizim from the building of altars by Abraham, Isaac, and Jacob, rather than the instructions for the sanctuary to be set up after the giving of the Torah, but this argument was in the air at the time. No matter how much confusion could be caused by disputing where Abraham and Isaac built altars, it could not be denied that Jacob built one either on the Mountain or right at the foot. More effectively, Jacob clearly recognises the status of the top of the Mountain, not a place at the foot, as the Gate of Heaven. Recognition by Jews of the effectiveness of arguing from Jacob’s vision and his recognition that the top of the Mountain is the Gate of Heaven or is just under the Gate of Heaven is shown in the pericope in Bereshit Rabba from the mid second century AD treated in my book on p. 81 to p. 82 top.

Sakte’s concern was only an extreme form of what everyone in both parties felt, both Sebuaeans and Dositheans. Bāba Rabba’s synagogue on the Meadow at the foot of the Mountain was a reminder of the Time of Favour. On this synagogue, see my book, Part II, pp. 36 to 38. I suggest that Bāba Rabba’s synagogue was put up with much the same rationale as what made the former Gorthenians keep using their Pavilion, after having accepted that some form of worship on the Mountain was allowed and obligatory in the present era. It would have been needed as a reminder that the Mountain had not been perfected, but would have been needed as well because it had some dim glow of the Time of Favour, making it both a comfort and a reminder of hope for perfection. It had to be on the Meadow, not on the Mountain, because it had to be an exact copy of a synagogue that had been put up in the Time of Favour. This building is not mentioned in the continuation of the work of A.F. If it had been standing, it would have been mentioned in the record of the troubles. It can be assumed that it was destroyed in 484 A.D. when the Christian Church manipulated the eastern Roman government to help it try to take over the virtue of Mt. Gerizim. See my book, pp. 110 to 113. ⁴

⁴ I now think I was wrong on pp. 37 and 38 of my book in saying the author of the Kitāb al-Kāfi, writing just before 1030 A.D., complained about people that lived near the Mountain going to Bāba Rabba’s synagogue on the Festivals when they could have gone up the Mountain. It was said above that this building is not mentioned in the continuation to the work of A.F., and that it had probably been destroyed in 484 A.D.

Deuteronomy XXVII:4 to 8 and the corresponding words at the end of the Ten Utterances command the setting up of stones on the Mountain and writing what is called “this Torah” on them.⁵ For a long while there was disagreement over whether the stones had been left on the Mountain but vanished during foreign rule, or whether they were not there because they had been taken back to Galgal, but in the end stones reappeared. **The ten stones marked a connection between the Torah and the Mountain, but not a union.** It could be argued that this connection marked by the stones would still be there even if the stones were removed, since the Torah only commands setting the stones up and writing on them, without specifying that the stones have to stay. However, Sakte would certainly have argued that the stones were not there because they had been moved and set up on the Meadow. The place on the Meadow where they were permanently set up would have had a connection with the dispensation inaugurated by Moses. It was asserted by some, and perhaps once thought by everyone, that there was a place called Galgal on the Meadow as well as the one near the Jordan. Marq knows of more than one Galgal. See my book, pp. 21 to 35. **This would have been part of Sakte’s argument for the legitimacy of the site of his pavilion. It would equally well have been an assertion that the Mountain’s holiness only came from the Torah.**

Later on a better way was found to have a reminder of the Time of Favour. The old part of the Abisha Scroll was said to have been written out in the Time of Favour. A.F. saw the opening of this scroll in the year of writing his book, 1355 A.D. He believed what was claimed. He said the scroll had the function of the Time of Favour, as well as being a sign that it would return. The scroll would have given a visible connection of the Time of Favour with the Torah, and a visible connection of the Torah with the Mountain. My own view is that any exemplar of the Torah has a glow of the Time of Favour regardless of when it was written out, because it will be copied from copies going back to exemplars written out in the Time of Favour. (Yes, I know this is not a historical argument. It still stands if you think about it).

With this increased veneration of the Mountain, the Dositheans were led to interact more with the Sebuaeans on the Mountain, even if they squabbled. This is documented from

⁵ **The paragraph after the Ten Utterances in the Samaritan Pentateuch about building an altar on Mt. Gerizim and setting up stones and writing on them was not put there by the Samaritans.** See my book, p. 28. The Samaritans did not reckon this paragraph as the last of the Ten Utterances till very late, contrary to assertions against evidence. See p. 17. **This paragraph was in the MT till very late.** See my book, p. 28. Related to this is the fact that **the reading “Mt. Gerizim” was in the MT in Deuteronomy XXVII:4 till the time of the Tanna’im.** See my book, pp. 21 to 35, for the proof and explanation of the circumstances. This indicates that the paragraph is not an addition by two separate sets of editors, and that its absence in the LXX is the sign of editing. (The omission could have been done in the translation, not the original. That can be put aside for the present purpose). A lot of guessing going nowhere has gone into trying to work out what is meant by the command to write out “this Torah” in Deuteronomy XXVII:4 to 8. All this guessing depends on the belief that the final editors of the Pentateuch were sloppy. The words “this Torah” in the paragraph after the Ten Utterances plainly refer to the Ten Utterances. The words “this Torah” in Deuteronomy plainly refer back to the same phrase in that paragraph. This is the kind of thing the editors did in Deuteronomy. This proposal is not negated by the fact that parts of the paragraph correspond to shorter pieces elsewhere. The short parts were needed elsewhere, but the whole paragraph was not. The parts of the paragraph hold together neatly.

the first centuries of Islam. See my article *Social Anomie*. This would have been new in Palestine but had started before then in Alexandria, at the end of the sixth century A.D. They did not squabble in Alexandria. See my book, p. 193. It is unlikely that Hadrian would have thought it useful to Rome to get on the good side of the Samaritans by spending money on the sanctuary if it had not been important to everyone. See my book, pp. 12 bottom to 13 top. Concern with the Mountain was not limited to one faction in 35 AD. See my book, p. 95.

The Sebuaeans and Dositheans definitively amalgamated at the start of the fourteenth century. The work of Abisha was promulgated soon afterwards. The word “promulgated” is right. The work has authority. This composition marked the definitive end of a long process by laying out all aspects of eschatology in the widest sense, including the nature of revelation and the nature of creation. For example, whereas the *Ṭubākh*, promulgated three hundred years before, had only had a short chapter on prophecy expressed in theoretical and exegetical terms, the new composition goes into detail and uses symbolic narrative about Moses. The choice of subject marked having reached completion because this was the very last thing that the two parties agreed on. This was more than seven hundred years after they stopped squabbling in Egypt, well over five hundred years since they stopped squabbling in Palestine, three hundred years or more after reaching enough agreement on the essentials of halachah to live together, and two or three hundred years after reaching agreement on most theology. (These dates can be established from the cooperation of both parties in Alexandria in getting what they wanted out of the Christian government right at the end of the sixth century; the accounts of squabbling in the seventh century and early eighth century in the continuation of the work of A.F.; the otherwise inexplicable fact that the sanctuary building was not put up again once Moslem rule had stabilised in the late eighth century A.D.; the need for the authoritative collections the *Kitāb aṭ-Ṭubākh* and *Kitāb al-Kāfi* in the early eleventh century; the careful wording in the *Kitāb al-Kāfi* in the early eleventh century about minor disagreements in halachah; the assumption in the *Kitāb aṭ-Ṭubākh* written right at the start of the eleventh century and the *Kitāb al-Kāfi* that there is no factional division over halachah; the assumption in both books that there is no factional division over basic theology; *the otherwise inexplicable absence of anything approaching eschatology in the Kitāb aṭ-Ṭubākh*; the date of the elaborate composition by Abisha; the Dosithean elements in the final orthodoxy in the work by Abisha; the indications in places in this work that what is said needs to be accepted by the reader; the incorporation of a collection called *Ildustān* in the liturgy (actually *ad-Dustān*, an Arabic title); the appearance of some important theological treatises in the thirteenth and fourteenth century; important work on hymns in the fourteenth century; the survival of different recensions of the book attributed to Marqē; ⁶ the survival up till the time of A.F. of the detailed record of developments between

⁶ It is generally assumed that the reason there are two recensions is that one is later than the other. There is no evidence for this. One recension has a slightly bigger proportion of old material than the other, and each recension has some old material that is not in the other one, and there are some differences in wording of the old material between the two recensions. In most places there is no reason for thinking one version of the wording to be older than the other, but in other places it can be either version that has what looks like the older version, or has the better version. The reason for one recension having a bigger proportion of old material is that it is shorter because it has less later material. **Both recensions have to be used** unless you just want to play games and get paid for it. The fashion is to use

factions within the Dosithean party, including the *exact words* of the essential formulation of position of each faction).

At this time the Sebuaeans were persuaded that the basic Dosithean premise was right, and there could not be a sanctuary building in the present era. The Dositheans accepted the Sebuaeans figure of the Tā'eb, now made less personal so as not to negate the work of Dositheos. The Sebuaeans agreed with the Dositheans that the sanctuary could not be rebuilt till the Tabernacle manifested itself on this level of existence and could be put in the sanctuary. Then the purpose of the sanctuary building was forgotten about in practice, and the building housing the Tabernacle was confused with the Tabernacle itself in practice. Long before the promulgation of Abisha's work, in reaction to Sakte, most Dositheans had probably agreed that the place where Jacob had his vision, Lūza, must have been on the Mountain, not on the Meadow. This datum can be derived by exegesis and need not be a bald assertion, though whether the exegesis is sound is another question. This datum --- and it really was seen as a datum because thought to be the plain intention of the text --- had implications and most Dositheans would have been relieved. Sakte's followers must have been convinced, since mentions of Gorthenians end with Epiphanius. (Later mentions by Christian authors are copies). All Dositheans would have been relieved at the renumbering of the Ten Utterances one thousand one hundred years after the reaction to Sakte. It gave them a way of being satisfied with worship on the Mountain, so that they could amalgamate with the Sebuaeans. The Sebuaeans had to announce the satisfactoriness of worship on the Mountain without any sanctuary building, but that would not have been a big step. They had not rebuilt the sanctuary when Moslem rule stabilised, and that was more than five hundred years before.

A.F. thought there had once been ten stones on the Mountain. The editors of the second recension of his book saw twelve. The tradition that there were twelve is ancient even if obviously not original. There is no explicit statement that there were ten from before the time of A.F., but the Arabic Joshua book leaves out all mention of this event. This book in its present form was meant to be acceptable to everyone, both Sebuaeans and Dositheans. The number of twelve stones would work for writing the Ten Utterances, if the heading went on a separate stone, and there was a coda as described in the Tosefta. See my book p. 35. If there were a coda it would have to be the paragraph after the Ten Utterances. (Remember this paragraph was not reckoned in as one of the ten at this time). **The number of twelve stones has the function of**

Tal's edition and ignore Ben-Ḥayyim's edition on the principle that anything done by a member of the cabal replaces all memory of anything done by anyone else. Specially if it is published by de Gruyter with imprimatur of the Führer of the cabal, the general editor of the series Studia Samaritana. There is no mention of Ben-Ḥayyim's edition in anything written in the Glorreiche Vaterland since Tal's edition of the other recension came out, and we won't be seeing any. Over and beyond getting the cabal to deign to let you in even if at a lower level than the half-dozen archons, there are some other perks. You don't have to let on that you don't know Hebrew well enough to read Ben-Ḥayyim's notes. You don't have to do so much work either. A few authors have had the courage to use Macdonald's translation. I say courage because without putting it into words they admit they have not got much Hebrew. All the same, none of these few, with one exception, bring up the difficulty that there are mistakes in Macdonald's translation. Only Daniel Olson has kept to the standards of research and got someone to check Macdonald's translation of passages used by him against Ben-Ḥayyim's translation and notes.

making an identification with the twelve stones from the Jordan bed set up on entering Canaan and accordingly the Time of Favour. This identification is secondary. A.F. knows the original tradition. See my book, pp. 21 to 35, at great length, on the whole question.

This leaves the question of how the editors of the second recension could have worked out how the words were spread over twelve stones, since by their time it had come to be accepted that the paragraph at the end of the Ten Utterances was not a coda but the tenth item on the list. It must have been supposed that the heading had been on a separate stone, and then either the two parts of the commandment against coveting had been on separate stones, or else the two parts of the first commandment, not having idols and not worshipping them, had been on separate stones. A.F. did not make this number of ten stones up. The Arabic Joshua book avoids saying how many stones were set up on the Mountain, leaving room for disagreement as to whether it was twelve or ten. If A.F. could say there had once been ten stones on the Mountain, the twelve stones there now could not have been there then. There must not have been any stones there. The Sebuaeans and Dositheans would have disagreed on how many stones there had been. The number of twelve allows identification of these stones with the ones taken from the bed of the Jordan and makes them a reminder of the Time of Favour **and a vestige of it.** This identification must be old because it is attested in the Jewish documentation as well. In my article *The Transmission of the Samaritan Joshua-Judges* I argued that this book was revised so as to be acceptable to both Sebuaeans and Dositheans, as part of the preparation for amalgamation. Now we can understand why A.F. said the Abisha Scroll **stands in for** the Time of Favour. Having this scroll with the old part thought to be from the Time of Favour in the synagogue on the Mountain gave a vestige of the Time of Favour acceptable to both parties, because it did not have to signify anything about the Mountain unless you wanted it to.

By the time the editors of the second recension worked, the dispute over the number of stones would have been forgotten. Twelve stones with ambiguous significance had been put up after A.F. wrote. At first they might have only been said to be memorials of the originals.

It can be shown that the sentences about Mt. Gerizim at the end of the Ten Utterances were not regarded as being the tenth on the list of the Ten Utterances in ancient times. Assertions that the verses were put there by the Samaritans can therefore be dismissed as the usual pseudo-scientific guesses without bothering to look at the evidence because anything distinctive to Samaritans must be made up so let's not bother. (The other supposed instances that were made using the assertion that anything Samaritan must be made up have been disposed of. Adrian Schenker has shown that the LXX originally had "the place the Lord chose" in all instances. It is not scientific to think that what is printed at the top of the page from old uncials must be the original. Hila Dayfani has given convincing evidence for the reading "Mt. Gerizim" in Deuteronomy XXVII:4 in a manuscript from Qumran. *4QpalaeoExod^m and the Gerizim Composition*. JBL 141:4, 2022, pp. 673 – 698. There is other textual evidence. I have given evidence that the Tanna'im changed the reading in my book, pp. 27 to 29 top and p. 32). This concept that the paragraph about Mt. Gerizim is the tenth of the Ten Utterances is not in the encomiums of the Mountain in the old part of the book attributed to Marqe or the old hymns, or the Kitāb at-Ṭubākh, compiled in about 1010 A.D. It was not much more than a hundred

years before Abisha's work that the renumbering happened. This can be seen from the disagreements on which part of the paragraph is the tenth item in the oldest mss. of the Torah that give a number to this part as if it were part of the list. **That means there was no tradition.** The oldest inscriptions giving a list of the Ten Utterances show the same uncertainty or disagreement. The oldest ms. to give a number to part of these sentences is dated 1215 A.D. It would not be safe to conclude that the concept behind the numbering appeared just at this time, since there are very few manuscripts of the Torah from this time or shortly earlier, and none that are much earlier. *If these sentences are read as part of the Ten Utterances, they make the whole of the Mosaic dispensation including the requirement of a sanctuary inseparable from the pre-existing holiness of the Mountain. This consequence is consistently overlooked.*

The Dositheans as a whole, defining their position in reaction to Sakte at the end of the first century A.D., formally announced the consequence of the top of the Mountain being permanently holy according to the Torah. This was congenial to the Sebuaeans. The attractiveness of Sakte's doctrine that the Mountain had no holiness without a sanctuary with the Mosaic Tabernacle was weakened. This does not mean the Ten Utterances were renumbered at that time. It does mean the renumbering centuries later would have been congenial to the Dositheans. It also made their union with the Sebuaeans easier. **The renumbering might have had this purpose.** Remember the renumbering is not a change to the text. The numbering is in the mind of the reader, or shown by the arrangement of lines, or in a study codex shown by marginal numbers not part of the text. (It needs to be worked out how the place of Dositheos and purpose of his work was redefined so as to allow full union. I hope to come back to this).

What happened to the Shechem Sacred Enclosure, the place of sacrifice belonging to the Qatṭīṭā'i, is not known. It was disused when Eusebius saw it or learnt about it, and no-one could tell him anything about it. We can guess with some probability if the thought of the time is considered. There was a tendency at the time to forget about any need for sacrifices. The Meadow could still have some glow of sacredness without sacrifices. The increased veneration of the Mountain would have affected the Qatṭīṭā'i as much as the followers of Sakte. I propose that it would have affected them more, and would have been compelling. The increased veneration of the Mountain was legitimised by taking note of a declaration by God *before the giving of the Torah*. Suddenly the acuteness of the occultation of the Tabernacle would have been relieved for the Qatṭīṭā'i along with the Dositheans. Suddenly there would have been no need for the Qatṭīṭā'i to revive the sacredness of the Meadow. All the apparatus of a place for sacrifices could be replaced by using the passages about Jacob. This is not a complete explanation of what happened. In the light of Olson's findings, it can be supposed that they expected Melchizedek or his line to do something, but we don't know what.

V. The Ebionites

Let's start with what the Ebionites might have known about what Jesus thought. Recovering what the real Jesus thought from what the Christian Church thought he must have thought or ought to have thought to suit Christianity is usually easy, but not in this case. Jesus seems to have agreed with Sakte's extreme position that not even prayer services on the

Mountain were valid in the present era, but were still required somewhere else.⁷ they had an entirely different view on the location, however. In chapter IV of John he is quoted as saying that the time of not worshipping on the Mountain but certainly worshipping somewhere else is already here. For any Samaritan worship in truth means worship in the right place. For Sakte this can't be Mt. Gerizim these days and never was Jerusalem. Worship in spirit means without sacrifices. Gone are the vaguely pious-sounding Christian words. Jesus did not see this as a solution. Anyone can see that the time is not here in the way needed. There is still irreconcilable disagreement between Samaritans and Jews. This remark is not an idle observation, but part of the statement of the difficulty of finding a solution by human ability. Jesus taught in the grounds of the Jerusalem temple. On the other hand, he predicted the end of it. We don't know what he meant by rebuilding it, since the editors of the gospels have no tradition and just guess. He might have been thinking of contact with the Heavenly Tabernacle. This is prominent in Samaritan thought, and exists in Jewish thought. The proof verse in the Torah is Exodus XXV:40. In my article *An Ancient Form of the Samaritan Concept of the Tā'eb* an argument is given for what Jesus saw as the only feasible provisional answer to disagreement between Samaritans and Jews that would never end but had to be made harmless so as to work towards starting the process of bringing the Time of Favour back. It is argued with evidence that there were two branches of the Ebionites, one Samaritan and one Jewish, working together in society and in friendly personal contact but worshipping separately. This confused Epiphanius more than usual. (We can't knock Epiphanius because his work is valuable. It's wearing to use, all the same). Look at the sputtering before his description of the Samaritan Ebionites. He had heard they behaved like Jews but were not Jews and behaved like Samaritans but were not Samaritans. This was on top of not knowing Samaritans and Jews behave pretty much the same and not knowing that followers of the real Jesus won't be called Christians.

⁷ Words of the Christian Jesus that sound vaguely pious have a sharp meaning coming from the real Jesus. There are some examples on p. 135 of my book of expressions in the Sermon on the Mount that are so vague as to be meaningless in the mouth of the Christian Jesus but are quite concrete in the mouth of the Israelite Jesus. What Christians find in ch. VII of Mark is not there. Jesus did not say nothing is unkosher. All Christian reading misrepresents what the words say. The Authorised Version is restrained in its dishonesty, but Evangelicals falsify the text to suit their man-made doctrine by adding a whole phrase or a whole clause with a verb, and disregarding grammar. See my book pp. 135 – 136. This is an example of how the Christian Church does not understand its own scriptures. Another good example is the lost sheep of the House of Israel. This is every single Israelite in the Time of Straying. It says the House of Israel because both Samaritans and Jews are meant. Another good example of making up fiction in the face of ignorance is the lamb of God. See pp. 15 and 16 of my article *An Ancient Form of the Samaritan Doctrine of the Tā'eb*. An explanation of most of what was not understood by Christians in their scriptures was dreamt up early on, but not this term. This term could never have been in the Ebionite writings that were snaffled because it has no meaning in the religion of Israel. No way of connecting it with the scriptures of the religion of Israel has ever been thought up. There are about five guesses at this, none of which work. One answer in folk thought is that it is the Passover lamb, but this is not a sacrifice in the sense needed. There is no way of connecting it with the Doctrine of the Atonement. In my article the lamb of God evaporates. The prize example is the expression “saving from sin”, which was in the Ebionite records used by Christianity with a meaning derived from Deuteronomy XXXIII:29 along with the explanation of the ending of the Time of Favour from general corruption and how it can return. The words were used to express a man-made concept inimical to the religion of Israel. I know this last statement of mine needs explanation and argument, but this is not the place.

The attitude of the Samaritan Ebionites to the Mountain is not known, but a careful look round brings up a good possibility. It is argued at length in Part II of my book that the Ebionites were not Christian, and are wrongly called such. Modern authors copy early Christian authors. They were followers of the real Jesus, not the Christian Jesus. Early Christian authors could not conceive that there was a difference. The Ebionites insisted that Jesus was concerned with Torah and mitsvot. See p. 64 of my book. A party with that outlook would have been concerned with Mt. Gerizim, even if they did not have access to it. Epiphanius in his description of heresy no. XXX says they have abandoned sacrifices. See my book, pp. 41 to 44. As usual, he does not understand his source. He forgets that no Jews or Samaritans have sacrifices at the time he writes. If he can be relied on, what he says is evidence that they agreed with Sakte that sacrifices are not allowed in the present era. He says they don't accept the passages about sacrifices in the Torah. *This is almost certainly a misunderstanding of a statement that they read these passages but without practising what is in them, because this is not the right time.* If this outlook goes back to Jesus, which it probably does, it would mean that Jesus largely agreed with Sakte on this. This might then mean he agreed with Sakte's conclusion that without a valid sanctuary and sacrifices, the parts of the rules of cleanness and uncleanness relevant to entering the sanctuary, the most serious grades, were not in effect, though other grades were. This would account for his apparent unconcern with becoming unclean by indirect contact, though there are other explanations. (The concept of uncleanness for only an indivisible point in time, which means for no length of time, is shown to exist in my book *Principles of Samaritan Halachah*. The words "it has an instant's effect" are used often in the Ṭubākh and Kāfi. The last grade of uncleanness goes away immediately. This might be relevant).

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А. С. Жамкочан, *Самаритянская Хроника Абу-л-Фатха из собрания Российской Национальной Библиотеки* (English title: *The Kitab at-Tarikh of Abu 'L-Fath (Samaritan Chronicle 1355 a.D. [sic])* Translated into Russian with Notes by Haroutun Jamgotchian). Moscow 1995. ISBN 5-7262-0203-1. The only competent translation into any language. A pdf can be downloaded from my colleague Helen Gael's Profile page on the Academia website. (But note that Vilmar's long detailed summary will do instead of a translation for some purposes). For political reasons this book is not listed by Pummer in his supposed complete survey of all aspects of Samaritan studies entitled *The Samaritans: A Profile*, published in 2016, though he had been told of it. Jamgotchian was not a member of the cabal and Stenhouse was a member. Jamgotchian's work is accurate and the English translation by Stenhouse is so bad as to be harmful, even where it seems to make sense. Jamgotchian's work was a threat and had to be kept hidden from the notice of the world. See my book, Part VII, on the long sordid story. Some others not in the club that were dangerously competent were treated the same way. On the case of Rudolf Macuch, see the entry on Tal's Aramaic primer in the Bibliography of my book. Jamgotchian was purposely and purposefully denied access to the full textual evidence. See Part VII of my book again.

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